

Study: Investigating ProjectQ retargetability

Implementation task

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In this study we will attempt to implement a new backend for the ProjectQ quantum compiler. ProjectQ claims to be retargetable, meaning the compiler is easily adaptable to new backends. We want to test this claim by having multiple people implement a new backend. After this you will be asked to rate the process. This will include rating documentation quality and invested time. Therefore, please **track the amount of time you invest in the implementation per step excluding breaks!**

Please attempt to implement this backend without the use of any material that is not explicitly mentioned here. There are supporting hints in case you get stuck during the implementation. Please also **record how many and which of these hints you required to successfully implement the backend!** Opened hints will be tracked on the hints HTML page.

Step 1: Getting to know ProjectQ

Please visit the [ProjectQ documentation page](#) to get a general overview of the project. Once you are satisfied, please:

- (a) Install `projectq` on your machine in a new project (`venv` recommended) using the `pip` package manager.
- (b) Study the ProjectQ documentation page and explore supported features, API documentation, and try to find a guide on how to implement a new backend.

We will implement a backend for a quantum simulator in this study. For the purpose of simplicity, we will not attempt a full implementation, but an implementation that can execute basic circuits. As you are supposed to rate the ProjectQ documentation, we will not give detailed instructions on how to implement this backend. Rather we ask you to use the available documentation and the provided hints if necessary.

Step 2: Getting to know the simulator

For this study we will implement a simple backend for the Stim simulator.

- (a) Visit the [Stim GitHub page](#). Please install the `stim` python package from this documentation page using `pip install stim` (in the same virtual environment as `projectq`).
- (b) Review the [getting started notebook](#) provided on the GitHub page. You can also visit this [documentation for Tableau](#), with special emphasis on the functions `from_circuit` and `to_state_vector`, which we will be using to simulate circuit execution with resulting state vectors, rather than using a sampling/shot-based approach.

Now that we know which simulator we want to implement, we need to focus on the actual implementation. For this study, we wish to implement a backend for the Stim simulator, which supports the following gates: X, Y, Z, H, CX. We will implement a bell curve testing circuit *using state vector simulation* to test if our backend implementation works as expected.

Step 3: Implementing the backend

Implement the basic structure for the backend. For this, follow these steps with reference to the ProjectQ documentation given above.

- (a) Create a `StimStudyBackend` class, that extends the ProjectQ `BasicEngine` class. For this scenario, assume we have a architecture supporting four qubits.
- (b) Implement all necessary functions using the ProjectQ documentation.

You have now created the backend implementation. Next, we will need to run circuits on our simulator. To the verify if the implementation is complete, we will create a test for the backend.

Step 4: Testing

Create a test function in which you execute the `test_bell` function, provided below. Make sure to install and import the `pytest` package.

```
def test_bell():
    from projectq import MainEngine
    from projectq.ops import H, Measure

    backend = StimBackend(verbose=True)
    engine = MainEngine(backend)

    qubits = engine.allocate_quireg(2)
    H | qubits[0]
    CNOT | (qubits[0], qubits[1])
    engine.flush()

    assert np.allclose (
        backend.get_result(),
        np.asarray([1, 0, 0, 1]) * 1 / np.sqrt(2)
    )
```

Once you have a backend class, that supports circuit execution with correct results for the given gate set, you have completed the implementation task. We now ask you to fill in a form on this implementation, rating the ProjectQ quantum compiler in its claims of retargetability.

Step 5: Rating implementation experience

Rate ProjectQ on the aspect of retargetability with reference to your implementation experience. For this, fill in the attached form and **please add freeform comments on the biggest hurdles and issues you encountered if not covered otherwise.**

After filling in the form, your participation in this study is completed. Thank you for your efforts!

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Rating ProjectQ retargetability

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Please fill in this form and rate the retargetability of ProjectQ based on your implementation experience. Give a rating with your reasoning for each of these questions.

Required Time per Step:	
Required Hints with Numbers:	

API and Documentation Analysis

The API and Documentation Analysis metric rates the accessibility, completeness, and clarity of a quantum compiler's API and additional documentation. This category is relevant for assessing how easily developers can understand and extend the compiler's capabilities, particularly in terms of implementing new backends.

1. **How experienced or inexperienced are you in the field of quantum software engineering?**

- Very experienced
- Somewhat experienced
- Neutral
- Somewhat inexperienced
- Very inexperienced

Reasoning:

2. **How experienced or inexperienced are you using ProjectQ in general?**

- Very experienced
- Somewhat experienced
- Neutral
- Somewhat inexperienced
- Very inexperienced

Reasoning:

3. **How experienced or inexperienced are you using/creating ProjectQ backends?**

- Very experienced
- Somewhat experienced
- Neutral
- Somewhat inexperienced
- Very inexperienced

Reasoning:

4. **How comprehensive or incomplete is the documentation in general?**

- Very comprehensive
- Somewhat comprehensive
- Neutral
- Somewhat incomplete
- Very incomplete

Reasoning:

5. **How comprehensive or incomplete is the documentation on implementing a new backend?**

- Very comprehensive
- Somewhat comprehensive
- Neutral
- Somewhat incomplete
- Very incomplete

Reasoning:

6. **How clear or unclear is the documentation on implementing a new backend?**

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear
- Neutral
- Somewhat unclear
- Very unclear

Reasoning:

7. **How comprehensive or incomplete is the documentation on supported features? This may include gate sets, frontends or backends.**

- Very comprehensive
- Somewhat comprehensive
- Neutral
- Somewhat incomplete
- Very incomplete

Reasoning:

8. **How easy or difficult is it to navigate the compilers documentation to find key information?**

- Very easy
- Somewhat easy
- Neutral
- Somewhat difficult
- Very difficult

Reasoning:

9. **How clear or unclear is the API?**

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear
- Neutral
- Somewhat unclear
- Very unclear

Reasoning:

10. **How easy or difficult would you rate the implementation process for the backend?**

- Very easy
- Somewhat easy
- Neutral
- Somewhat difficult
- Very difficult

Reasoning:

11. **How necessary or unnecessary were the hints for your success in implementing the backend?**

- Very necessary
- Somewhat necessary
- Neutral
- Somewhat unnecessary
- Very unnecessary

Reasoning:

12. Which elements of the documentation were most helpful to your success in implementing the backend?

13. Which elements of the documentation were most lacking, hindering your success in implementing the backend?

14. Note down any further comments regarding the implementation process here.